

Varietal resistance and chemical control of thrips in West Bengal, India

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In July 1976, a severe outbreak of thrips *Baliothrips biformis* occurred in the nurseries at the Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, West Bengal. About 90% of the seedlings showed leaf-rolling and yellowing in the upper half of the leaves. The graminaceous weed *Paspalum scorbiculatum* surrounding the nursery bunds harbored the thrips. Rainfall during seedling growth was below normal, but the nurseries were kept wet throughout the period by repeated irrigation. In a National Screening Nursery set of 394 entries, only IET 5973, IET 6003, and IET 6004 had minimum infestation (score = 3 on a 1–9 scale). Three other entries scored 9 and had considerable seedling mortality. No entry was free from attack.

The thrips problem in the 1977 nurseries was similar, although rainfall was normal. Six insecticides — phosalone, methyl demeton, fenitrothion, thiometon, Isufenphos, and phenthoate —

were tested to check the infestation. Among them thiometon at 0.02% concentration was quite effective. At

the tillering stage, the plants had no symptoms of thrips damage but showed a preponderance of bacterial blight.

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Deep water

Algae living on deep water rice in Bangladesh

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Stem sections, including nodal roots and leaf sheaths, were removed from deep-water rice in a field at Keraniganj, central Bangladesh, in mid-August and early September 1977. The variety, Chota Bawalia, had been flooded for 3.5 months and was in the late vegetative stage. The water was 1.5 m deep. Twenty-four species of algae were identified from this material: 12 Cyanophyta, 4 Chlorophyta,

and 8 Chrysophyta.

The following 5 Cyanophyta species are known as nitrogen fixing algae:

Species	Substrate	Relative abundance ^a
<i>Anabaena unispora</i> var. <i>catlingii</i> var. nov.	roots	X
<i>Scytonema</i> coactile	roots	X
<i>Plectonema</i> tomasinianum	stem	X
<i>Calothrix</i> marchica	roots	XX
<i>Microchaeta</i> robusta	roots, leaf sheaths	X

^ax = rare, xx = moderate.

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Rice germplasm from the higher Himalayan hills of Uttar Pradesh, India

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More than 600 rices have been collected in a germplasm conservation project in the Himalayan hills of Uttar Pradesh. The highest altitude at which rice is grown in these hills is 1,820 m.

Nine rices were collected from altitudes higher than 1,700 m. Three — Jaulia, Swag, and Laugiri — were collected in Gwaldam, Chamoli district, at 1,819 m. Three others — Chaurdhan, Gyarsu, and Chari — were collected from Kutnaur, Uttarkashi district, at about

1,700 m. Another three — Bomki, Bhagwaunaj, and Jadhkia — were collected from Bhatwari, Uttarkashi district, also at about 1,700 m. All collections were from rainfed upland

fields, which are sown around mid-March and harvested in mid- to late September. The cultivars are being further purified, tested, and multiplied. Their grain characteristics are in the table.

Grain characteristics of cultivars collected at altitudes higher than 1,700 m in the Himalayan hills of Uttar Pradesh, India.

Cultivar	Grain type	Abdominal white	Pericarp color	Aroma
Jaulia	Long, bold	Absent	Light red	None
Swag	Short, bold	Present	White	None
Laugiri	Long, bold	Absent	Mild red	None
Chaurdhan	Long, bold	Absent	Deep red	None
Gyarsu	Medium, slender	Absent	White	None
Chari	Short, bold	Absent	Light red	None
Bomki	Long, bold	Absent	White	Aromatic
Bhagwaunaj	Long, bold	Absent	Light red	None
Jadhkia	Long, bold	Absent	Light red	None